

Report of the Inaugural Scientific Advisory Board Session for the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics Literature Services (SIBiLS)

Date: Dec the 10th, 2024

Location: online

Present SAB members: Laurence Benichou, Dietrich Rebholz-Schuhmann, Melissa Harrisson, Robert Waterhouse, Donat Agosti, Nona Naderi

Present SIBiLS members: Patrick Ruch, Déborah Caucheteur, Julien Gobeill, Anaïs Mottaz, Emilie Pasche

1. Synthesis

The SAB members acknowledge that a lot of progress has been made and the achievements are significant. Several information retrieval solutions exist side by side for biodiversity, genomic variation and others. The solutions have a sound technical background and are delivered through user interfaces and APIs. Although a systematic capturing of users is still an open issue, the user numbers speak in favour of the presented solutions.

2. Recommendations

The recommendations are the following:

1. One of the open points raised towards the SAB was the question, how SIBiLS can develop and improve its services and standings. This was passed back to the SIBiLS team, since it is the task of the team to define a strategy for itself and build the perspective for further developments. This is the natural basis for such a project and such a team to get feedback on the strategy in the first place and then develop towards a future vision and outcome.
2. It is also advised (see previous point) to seek input from users and user groups. This is a big ask, since this generates overheads without always a clear outcome. However, it is worth the effort to get engaged with the community, and to raise awareness, and to support further developments of the services and the strategy,
3. Any competition with similar or related literature services is not seen as a concern by the SAB, since SIBiLS has sufficient unique value proposition and sufficient user interest has been documented, although the capturing of usages still has to be improved (as stated from the team itself). In fact collaboration with resources such as Europe PMC would build the combined strength of both resources. Furthermore, it is not so clear, whether the US is not steering away from delivering such services to the general public (new Trump era) and therefore European efforts for information provision have to be kept up for the scientists. The use of the name "PMC" must be clarified, i.e. whether the acronym PMC can be used freely. Make sure that this is the case, and change otherwise.
4. The team has engaged into the development and use of Knowledge Graphs. This is very good and state of the art and is also driven by initiatives in the life science community to deliver knowledge through ontologies. It is important to share this experience with other communities working on knowledge graphs (e.g., TIB Germany and EMBL-EBI in the UK). In a certain sense, the data representation could be called a model (well be cautious about this term), and it is important to share this with other teams working on knowledge graphs in the life science domain. This inspires shared developments and gives the

opportunity to integrate data across sites. Do teaching, give talks, learn about the approaches from others, learn how to share data. Good opportunities arise on the European level (see Elixir) and on the German level (see NFDI initiatives and de.NBI).

5. With regard to biodiversity: there is a strong community in Germany building data resources for biodiversity (NFDI for biodiversity, Bremen University, DSMZ / Braunschweig, Senckenberg Museum and EMBL-EBI, the Biodiversity portal). SIBiLS should build relationships with the different players.
6. The collaborative work with the data repositories is very valuable (Zenodo, Plazi, Pensoft). It is clear that all restrictions to access the data is hurtful, but the only way to work around this is to get in touch with the consortium / people running the repositories. This has been initiated and should develop into a fruitful collaboration. Collaboration with BioStudies would also be beneficial.
7. The SIBiLS team is exploring Large Language Models and Knowledge Graphs. Both are strong research fields and the combination of both is even more challenging. It is unclear which direction the research is going, however it is a great opportunity to explore where the team can profit from the technologies or even initiate their own research.
8. GRID should be replaced by ROR and accession numbers such as specimen and GRSciColl (<https://scientific-collections.gbif.org/>) should be added.
9. Shape any query interfaces in a way that regular users can profit from them. Python queries, JSON queries or SPARQL queries are powerful but only advanced users can leverage it, and being able to shape powerful queries through an interface and RESTful services - and via the SPARQL endpoint - is needed.

3. Future SAB organisation

The SAB also agrees that the next SAB meeting could be organized as a f2f event in Geneva.